

Research Article

Preparation of Eco-Friendly Coffee Scrub from Spent Coffee Grounds

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Abstract: *The increasing demand for natural products has driven significant interest in utilizing waste materials as primary ingredients in the cosmetic industry. With the rising global consumption of coffee, the accumulation of spent coffee grounds has become a growing environmental concern. This study addresses this issue by preparing a body scrub using spent coffee grounds and evaluating its spreadability, odor, color, and pH to determine its suitability for skincare applications. Three formulations were developed using varying proportions of sugar, baking soda, and spent coffee grounds. The results demonstrate that ingredient ratios significantly impact the scrub's physical characteristics and overall user experience. Notably, the sample with reduced sugar content exhibited a smoother texture, making it more suitable for a wider audience, including individuals with sensitive skin. Formulation 2 emerged as the most effective formulation, achieving the highest spreadability (4.53 cm), a balanced pH of 5, and a smooth, slightly oily texture that left the skin feeling soft and moisturized — ideal for sensitive skin. In contrast, Formulation 1, with its gritty texture, proved too abrasive, while Formulation 3, which contained baking soda, had a less acidic pH (6) and a powdery texture, providing moderate exfoliation. These findings highlight the potential of spent coffee grounds as a sustainable, eco-friendly alternative in skincare formulations, contributing to the advancement of environmentally conscious cosmetic products while offering a practical solution for coffee waste management.*

Keywords: *Eco-friendly; spent coffee grounds; scrub; exfoliating agent; sustainability*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Coffee is one of the most widely consumed beverages worldwide, with increasing popularity in non-traditional coffee-drinking regions such as Oceania and Asia. However, its high consumption generates significant environmental concerns (Samoggia & Riedel, 2019). Each year, approximately 6 million tons of spent coffee grounds (SCG) are discarded, with most ending up in landfills, contributing

to greenhouse gas emissions and waste management challenges (Costa et al., 2022; Sousa & Ferreira, 2018). Despite being treated as waste, SCG contains valuable bioactive compounds, such as phenolics, caffeine, and chlorogenic acid, which possess antioxidant and exfoliating properties, making them suitable for cosmetic applications.

Additionally, SCG exhibits anti-inflammatory properties, reducing redness, swelling, and acne. Meanwhile, caffeine’s vasoconstrictive effect temporarily tightens the skin, minimizing puffiness and cellulite, making SCG a popular ingredient in eyelid scrubs (Dave et al., 2022; Soon, 2024). When combined with fragrant oils, their exfoliating abilities help remove dead skin cells, resulting in a smoother and more radiant complexion while enhancing the sensory experience of skincare applications (Errico et al., 2023). Compared to other natural exfoliants such as sugar, salt, and walnut shells, SCG provides a coarser scrubbing action, making it particularly effective for skin renewal while offering additional antioxidant benefits (Rodrigues et al., 2023). The chlorogenic acids present in SCG further enhance their role in skincare formulations, solidifying their potential as a sustainable and multifunctional cosmetic ingredient. Unlike synthetic microbeads, which contribute to marine pollution, SCGs are biodegradable and environmentally friendly (Rodrigues et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2022).

This study aims to formulate a body scrub utilizing SCG and evaluate its physical properties, including spreadability, odor, color, and pH. This study promotes sustainability by repurposing coffee waste into skincare ingredients while showcasing SCG’s potential in eco-friendly cosmetic applications.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Materials

The materials used in the preparation of coffee scrub are spent coffee grounds, sugar, baking soda, sunflower oil, coconut oil, preservative (Germall™ Plus), fragrance (Coffee fragrance, Evoke Occu), emulsifying wax (Polawax GP-200), and shea butter. The preparation ratios for each ingredient are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Preparation ratios of ingredients used for eco-friendly coffee scrub

Materials	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Spent coffee ground (g)	7.0	15.0	7.0
Sugar (g)	15.0	10.0	-
Baking soda (g)	-	-	50.0
Sunflower oil (mL)	35.0	35.0	35.0
Coconut oil (mL)	12.0	12.0	12.0
Preservative (mL)	1.0	1.0	1.0
Fragrance (mL)	5.0	5.0	5.0
Emulsifying wax (g)	20.0	20.0	20.0
Shea butter (g)	11.0	11.0	11.0

2.2 Preparation of coffee scrub

Sunflower oil, coconut oil, emulsifying wax, and shea butter were placed in a beaker and heated on a hot plate at a low heat. The contents were stirred with a glass rod until fully melted. After removing the beaker from the heat, the spent coffee grounds, sugar (and baking soda for Sample 3) were gradually

added to the melted mixture while stirring to ensure even distribution and proper texture. Preservatives and fragrance were added to the mixture, followed by further stirring for a homogenous blend. The final mixture was transferred into airtight jars, labelled with sample numbers, and stored at room temperature for 24 hours before testing.

2.3 Physical test of coffee scrub

The coffee scrub was tested for spreadability, color, texture, odor, and pH.

2.3.1 Spreadability test

For each sample, 2 g of scrub was placed on a clean white tile. A 250 mL beaker filled with water was placed on the scrub for 7 seconds to ensure uniform spreading. The diameter of the spread was then measured using a ruler (Figure 1). This procedure was repeated three times, and the average spread diameter was calculated.

Figure 1. Spreadability test for coffee scrub after being placed on white tiles and the spread diameter measured using a ruler.

2.3.2 Color, texture, after-wash feeling, and odor test

The color, texture, after-wash feeling, and fragrance of each sample were observed and recorded through visual inspection and sensory evaluation.

2.3.3 pH test

The pH of the scrubs was determined using pH indicator strips. The scrub was smeared onto the strip and gently pressed to ensure good contact. After a few seconds, the resulting color change on the strip was compared with a color chart to determine the pH.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

All scrub samples were observed for their color and texture and weighed to determine their mass.

3.1 The mass, color, texture, and after-wash feeling of the coffee scrub

All scrubs have varied mass, with sample 2 being the lightest (103.7739 g) and sample 3 being the heaviest (134.5778 g) (Table 2). The differences in mass may be due to variations in the formulation. For sample 2, 15.37 g of SCG was added, which is approximately 8.34 g more SCG than in sample 1 and sample 3. However, sample 3 was the heaviest not because of its SCG content, but due to the addition of 50.0 g of baking soda, which significantly contributed to its weight. In contrast, sample 1 (134.5778 g) contained 15.02 g of coarse-grain sugar, while sample 2 contained 10.05 g of finely ground sugar. The

differences in secondary ingredients like sugar and baking soda, alongside the SCG content, influenced the overall mass of the scrub.

The color differences are due to varying amounts of SCG used in each formulation. Sample 1, with moderate SCG content (7.03 g), appeared greyish brown, while sample 3, with almost the same amount of SCG content as sample 1 (7.04 g), resulted in a lighter greyish brown color due to the addition of 50.0 g of baking soda. On the other hand, sample 2, with the highest SCG content (15.37 g), appeared a darker woody brown color (Figure 2).

Table 2. The mass, color, texture, and after-wash feeling of the coffee scrub

Sample	Mass of coffee Scrub (g)	Color	Texture	After-wash feeling
1	117.7689	Greyish brown	Very harsh and gritty	Harsh on skin
2	103.7739	Woody brown	Smooth and oily	Soapy and skin feels smooth
3	134.5778	Light greyish brown	Smooth and powdery	A bit oily but skin feels smooth

Figure 2. Coffee scrub sample 1, sample 2, and sample 3

For the texture analysis, sample 1 was harsh and gritty in texture, as it used coarse-grain sugar and a moderate amount of SCG. This sample may be suitable for those seeking deep exfoliation, but the harshness can feel abrasive on the skin, thus not suitable for sensitive skin (Duarte et al., 2017). Sample 2 was a mixture of finely ground sugar, which became smoother and oilier in texture, thus providing a gentler finish compared to sample 1. On the other hand, sample 3 was smooth and powdery because of the addition of baking soda. This sample is ideal for mild exfoliation, hence more suitable for sensitive skin.

Upon evaluation after washing, sample 1 had a coarse and gritty texture, which was felt to be quite harsh on the skin. These characteristics can raise the chances of over-exfoliation, which may irritate sensitive skin and further deteriorate its condition (Hussein et al., 2024). On the other hand, sample 2 had a soapy and smooth feel that cleaned well and was pleasing in texture. Sample 3, on the other hand, had a bit oilier texture but was able to leave the skin smooth after use, a sure indication of mild exfoliation coupled with lock-in moisture. For this reason, it would be an excellent choice for dry skin. Kang et al. (2022) and Marlina et al., (2022) noted that the after-wash feeling itself is a selling point of any skincare product. Hence, the fresh, smooth sensation created by sample 2 underlines the importance of adding active moisturizing ingredients to give it more consumer appeal.

3.1 The odor, pH, and the spreadability of the coffee scrub

All the samples were added with 5 ml of coffee fragrance. However, the odors of the coffee scrubs displayed slight but noticeable differences, which are likely influenced by their formulations and ingredients. Sample 1 has a pleasant nutty smell, typical for a coffee scrub, although its coffee fragrance is not that strong. Sample 2 exhibited a nutty odor but with a slightly unpleasant undertone, which might be attributed to ingredient imbalance or possible oxidation during preparation or storage (Freskayani et.al, 2022). Subsequently, sample 3 retained the most appealing and distinct coffee aroma, likely due to the inclusion of baking soda. The addition of baking soda may have helped preserve the freshness of the coffee scent (Sen, 2021). Future studies should focus on adjusting sample 2's formulation to achieve a pleasant nutty scent, similar to that of sample 1, or the distinct coffee aroma found in sample 3. An attractive scent will likely draw more consumers to the products. Table 3 shows the odor, pH value, and spreadability observed for the prepared coffee scrub.

Table 3. The odor, pH value and spreadability of the coffee scrub

Sample	Odor	pH value	Spreadability (cm)
1	Nutty smell	5	3.07
2	Nutty smell but slightly unpleasant	5	4.53
3	Coffee smell	6	3.57

The pH test results indicated that both sample 1 and sample 2 had a pH of 5, while sample 3 had a slightly higher pH of 6. Recent investigations measuring skin surface pH in healthy individuals report an average pH ranging from 4.1 to 5.8 (Costa & Horswill, 2022). Suggesting that samples 1 and 2 are likely more compatible with maintaining skin barrier integrity and are less likely to cause irritation. Although sample 3's pH is slightly more alkaline, it still falls within the acceptable limits for cosmetic skincare products. However, high pH might affect the skin microbiome in the long run (Lukić et al., 2021). Second, the pH of the scrub should be brought to the level of human skin's natural acidity. Thus, the pH of sample 2, which was 5, allows it to be compatible with the skin barrier and, therefore, mild and efficient, which is an important issue for consumer satisfaction and comfort.

In terms of spreadability, sample 2 has the longest diameter at 4.53 cm, followed by sample 3 with 3.57 cm, and sample 1 is the smallest at 3.07 cm. This is because of the differences in the composition of each scrub. Sample 2, having a smooth and oily texture, greatly enhances its spreadability, making it most viable upon application. In contrast, sample 1 is harsh and gritty, with less spreadability, and hence is not comfortable to apply. As Pal et al. (2024) commented, "the texture and spreadability of the scrub are both critical in terms of market acceptability." The smooth, oily texture and high spreadability of sample 2 guarantee ease of application, minimum product wastage, cost-effectiveness, and user-friendliness in application. These qualities make it appealing to a broad range of consumers, especially those with sensitive skin.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that SCG is a viable and sustainable exfoliant, making it a key ingredient in eco-friendly body scrubs. Among the formulations tested, Sample 2 emerged as the optimal formulation, containing the highest SCG content (15.37 g). This resulted in a woody brown color, a smooth, oily texture for gentler exfoliation, and superior spreadability (4.53 cm diameter). Additionally, its pH value of 5.0 makes it suitable for various skin types, including sensitive skin. With

its enhanced texture, skin compatibility, and marketability, Sample 2 aligns with sustainable skincare practices, reinforcing the potential of SCG-based cosmetics as an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic exfoliants. Future studies should focus on optimizing SCG particle size to enhance the texture and uniformity of the scrub, ensuring a smoother and more consistent application. Additionally, improving fragrance quality through natural scent boosters or advanced scent-masking techniques could enhance the product's appeal. Addressing these aspects will further refine SCG-based skincare products, making them more effective and commercially viable while maintaining environmental sustainability.

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